

**THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS ON
THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF CIVIL SOCIETY IN THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN**

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Annotation: This article analyzes the reforms implemented in the years of independence in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the formation of civil society in the application of social innovations and ensuring the well-being of citizens.

Key words: idea, innovation, social innovation, Uzbek model civil society institutions, civil society, urbanization, intellectual potential, ecological problem, smart city, energy, logistics, health care, social protection.

Enter

As a result of the reforms carried out in our country, public initiative and control over state agencies, in which public initiatives and control over state agencies play a decisive role, have a solid economic basis, democratic values have been established, cultural heights have been achieved, and democratic methods of management have been formed. the role of citizens' self-management agencies is constantly increasing, the role and importance of social innovations in society is increasing.

Social innovations include a set of new strategies, concepts, ideas, and organizations

aimed at meeting any needs of society and lead to social changes in society.

Views on social innovation began to be discussed in the 60s of the 20th century in the views of scientists such as Peter Drucker and Michael Young. By the 70s, this term began to be used in the scientific and creative works of French scientists. Nevertheless, the views on social innovation and its concepts began to be researched a little before the scientific works of these scientists. For example, Benjamin Franklin emphasized the importance of small social organizations that help solve everyday problems, while Robert Owen, the founder of trade unions and a supporter of innovation in the social sphere, Karl Marx, Max Weber and other representatives of the social sphere have emphasized that social news is an important factor in the development of society [1].

If we take into account that the 20th century was the age of social innovations, the improvement of working conditions of people, the expansion of opportunities to find new solutions to the problems facing the society, gave impetus to the distribution of social innovations throughout the world.

Social innovations are developing under the motto of working together towards a sustainable society in social research organizations, companies or all-round independent organizations.

The idea of social innovation occupies an important place in the socially oriented state policy of developed countries. In them, the state and the private sector are developing areas such as social responsibility and social entrepreneurship in cooperation.

The goal of most countries is to reduce the philanthropic policy of the state by giving more support to social innovators or social entrepreneurs and inventors rather than

identifying them. However, this situation is determined by the transfer of a certain part of the socially oriented policy of the states to the socially active population or civil society institutions.

"The emergence or use of social innovations is caused by certain processes in the social sphere, including:

- the acceleration of existing social problems requires solving this problem in a new way; As an example of these processes, when our country gained independence, a very unstable social situation arose in our country. The population growth rate was three times higher than the former Soviet Union average. Moreover, labor resources were growing twice as fast as the average growth rate of the population. In the end, the unemployment rate increased, and the income of the population fell sharply. This process brought the implementation of a unique new social policy to the level of the demand of that time;
- the lack of resources for the development of the social sphere leads to the use of more effective means in this sphere; In such a case, the further improvement of social relations is caused not only by natural resources, but also by the human factor, the state of providing sufficient funds, the limitation of time and distance, and the lack of transport factors;
- increase in demand for the quality of services provided in the social sphere, or adaptation to international standards. The increase in service requirements in the social sphere increases the need for innovative services" [2].

Today, based on the demands and needs of social innovations, social innovations are classified as follows:

"First of all, social innovations are divided into complex and local social

innovations according to the scope of social factors. In this direction, social factors are determined based on the scope of the regions. For example, a social problem in a certain region may not apply to the entire Republic, or the same problem may exist in the entire Republic.

Secondly: it is carried out by applying innovations in the spheres of society's life: political, economic, cultural, spiritual and social.

Thirdly, innovation during the implementation period is carried out in a strategic and tactical way.

Fourthly: on the formation of social direction in the organization, it is implemented through the working conditions, cultural level of employees and the existing social infrastructure in the enterprise.

Fifth: social innovations aimed at solving internal and external social problems according to the state of implementation.

Sixth: material, organizational and cultural social innovations according to the form of implementation. seventh: one-time social innovations aimed at a particular object and widespread social innovations aimed at several objects, according to the scope of use.

Eighth: according to the purpose, it is divided into innovations aimed at updating the principle of activity and innovations aimed at organizing new product activities" [3].

The classification of social innovations according to the above structure, in turn, shows their areas of application. Therefore, social innovations are used in social spheres.

First: in areas aimed at increasing the living conditions, employment and income of

the population; secondly: in the field of healthcare system; thirdly: in the field of education; fourthly: in areas aimed at raising the cultural level of the population; fifthly: in areas aimed at social protection of the population; sixth: in areas aimed at providing housing to the population; seventh: in the field of public safety; eighth: in the field of environmental protection; ninth: in the field of communication services; tenth: it is used in the fields of supporting low-income families, the elderly, children in need of protection, and the disabled. "Currently, new tasks are facing the reform of statehood, which is the most important subject of the democratic political system. This is explained, first of all, by the fact that at the current stage, the tasks of further democratization of society's life have become important and urgent based on the diversity of political institutions and non-state social associations and their role strengthening, as well as the increase in political activity of the population. Huge changes are taking place in Uzbekistan - the stage of development of a free and fair civil society based on a legal democratic state and a socially oriented market economy. In the conditions of democratization of public life, it is natural to pay more attention to the problems of democratic order and sustainable development. Because this process requires fundamental changes in all spheres, from politics to spirituality, from wages to state administration, and making innovations appropriate to the times" [4]. Fulfillment of these requirements has been one of the priorities of our state's policy since the first years of our independence.

At this point, it should be noted that in 1990, only 31% of the state budget expenditures in our country were directed to the financing of social spheres. In 1992, 35.43% of the state budget was spent on cultural and social activities, this figure was 37.79% in 1993, 43.03% in 1994, 45.29% in 1995, and more than 50% in 2008. In

2015, about 60% of the funds from the state budget are directed to the social sector. It is noteworthy that 34% of it is aimed at education and 15% at health [5]. In 2023, 129,891 billion soums will be allocated to the social sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which in turn is 50.4% of the total State budget expenditures [6]. In the current era of deepening democratic reforms, building a developed and free civil society, and modernizing all spheres of our nation's life, the reforms in all spheres are being carried out for the well-being of our nation, based on the principle of "Strategy of actions - towards a developed civil society". It is necessary to take into account the importance of social innovations and social innovations.

The innovative activity of the institutions of the civil society is primarily aimed at the formation of a person who lives independently and conducts his activities in the 21st century technologies and social development processes. In this regard, cooperation between state and civil institutions can be effective in cases where: allocating a number of benefits (financial assistance, tax benefits, information provision, etc.) by the state to effectively organize the activities of civil society institutions implementing social innovations;

- creating an opportunity for citizens with social innovation initiative to implement their ideas as a direction of the state social policy (establishing expert and public councils, monitoring and evaluating the activities of state management bodies, public hearings, drawing the attention of the government focusing on existing social problems);
- to ensure social stability and national security, innovative forms of working with different layers of the population, and effective use of the potential of civil society

institutions. In this regard, social innovations are one of the most promising tools that can provide civil society and intersectoral partnership to solve social problems. Social innovations bring significant benefits to society by creating a new form of communication between society and the state.

Summary

Our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev "First of all, effective use of mechanisms for timely registration of persons in need of social protection and permanent assistance, monitoring and support from the moment signs of need appear, including the social condition of such persons using modern information and communication technologies. recalling that it is necessary to pay special attention to effective monitoring, comprehensive assessment of their living conditions, development and implementation of individual development programs, as well as improvement of the system that allows providing necessary support in time" [7] must

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